

D3.1

PoDIUM Platform Architecture Description

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547
Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Type of deliverable	R – Document, report
Work package	WP3 – Technical innovation and development
Deliverable number	D3.1 PoDIUM platform architecture description
Status - version, date	V1.0, 22/09/2023
Deliverable leader	UULM
Contractual date of delivery	30/09/2023
Keywords	PoDIUM, architecture, communication, functions, data flow, IT, trust

Contributors

Name	Organisation
Alessio Claudio	LINKS
Alexander Scheible	UULM
Andrea Vesco	LINKS
Bernhard Monschiebl	ATE
Daniele Brevi	LINKS
David Porcuna	AAE
Emily Stevens	ATE
Federico Princiotta	LINKS
Guido Gavilanes	LINKS
Harilaos Vasiliadis	AAE
Jacint Castells	IDIADA
Jordi Casademont	UPC
Jordi Marias	i2CAT
Jorge Suárez	ETRA
Lazaros Gkatzikis	ICCS
Manuel Serrano	ETRA
Manuel Vivó	ETRA
Marcel Kern	NOKIA
Markus Wimmer	NOKIA
Martin Dirnwoeber	ATE
Michael Buchholz	UULM
Steffen Schulz	NOKIA
Tobias Müller	Bosch
William Diego	RETEVISION
Zhou Yu	Bosch

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Jordi Casademont	UPC	23/08/2023
Peer review 2	Lazaros Gkatzikis	ICCS	15/09/2023

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of changes
0.1	30/06/2023	Alexander Scheible	First draft of document structure + chapter 1 introduction
0.2	30/06/2023	Alexander Scheible	Second draft based on F2F Barcelona
0.3	31/07/2023	Alexander Scheible	First version with all inputs merged
0.4	09/08/2023	Alexander Scheible	Merged version after updates and comments from all involved partners
0.5	10/08/2023	Alexander Scheible	Updated version after issue solution telco
0.6	11/08/2023	Alexander Scheible Michael Buchholz	Version ready for internal review
0.7	19/09/2023	Alexander Scheible Michael Buchholz	Integration of reviewers' feedback
1.0	22/09/2023	Alexander Scheible Michael Buchholz	Final preparations for submission/publication

Legal Disclaimer

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority, CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The information in this document is provided "as is", and no guarantee or warranty is given that it is fit for any specific purpose. The PoDIUM project Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Copyright © PoDIUM Consortium, 2023.

Table of contents

Contents

- Contributors..... 3**
- Quality Control..... 4**
- Version History 4**
- Legal Disclaimer 4**
- List of figures..... 7**
- List of abbreviations and acronyms..... 8**
- Executive Summary 10**

- 1. Introduction 11**
 - 1.1. Project Introduction 11
 - 1.2. Purpose of the deliverable 11
 - 1.3. Intended audience..... 12
 - 1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables . 12

- 2. High-Level Architecture 13**

- 3. Communication View 15**
 - 3.1. Overview..... 15
 - 3.2. Levels of Communication 15
 - 3.3. Communication Technology..... 16
 - 3.4. Type of Communication 18
 - 3.5. Platform Communication Architecture View 18

- 4. Functional View 20**
 - 4.1. Overview..... 20
 - 4.2. Platform Services Functions 20
 - 4.3. Road User Functions..... 21
 - 4.4. Sensors and Actors Functions..... 23

- 5. Data Flow and Storage View..... 25**
 - 5.1. Overview..... 25
 - 5.2. Data Flow and Storage components description 25

- 6. IT Environment View 33**
 - 6.1. Overview..... 33
 - 6.2. IT components description..... 33

- 7. Software Integrity and Data Truthfulness..... 36**

7.1.	Software Integrity.....	36
7.2.	Data Truthfulness	38
8.	Conclusions	40
	References	41

List of figures

Figure 1 High-level architecture	13
Figure 2: High-level communication view platform architecture.	15
Figure 3: Communication view platform architecture.	19
Figure 4: Overview of the functional view.	20
Figure 5: Overview of Road Users functions.	22
Figure 6: Overview Sensors and Actor Functions.....	23
Figure 7: Overview of the data flow view.	26
Figure 8: IT environment view of platform architecture.....	33
Figure 9: High-level remote attestation architecture for verification of software integrity.....	36
Figure 10: Software Integrity Architecture within the TCB and Remote Attestor Architecture.....	37
Figure 11: General data truthfulness approach.	38
Figure 12: Self-assessment for the Digital Twin.	38
Figure 13: Sensors' fusion and enhancement	39

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
5G	5 th Generation
AK	Attestation Key
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAV	Connected Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CV	Connected Vehicle
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (LTE-PC5)
DB	Database
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DT	Digital Twin
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EV	Emergency Vehicle
FR	Frequency Range
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HW	Hardware
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IMA	Integrity Measurement Architecture
IT	Information Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
IVIM	In-Vehicle Information Messages
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LL	Living Lab
LTE	Long Term Evolution

MAP	MAP Extended Message
MCM	Manoeuvre Coordination Message
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
NIC	Network Interface Card
OBU	On-Board Unit
OB-PC	On-Board Personal Computer
P2M	Point-to-Multipoint
P2P	Point-to-Point
PCR	Platform Configuration Registers
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
RSU	Road-Side Unit
SA	Standalone
SL	Sidelink
SPATEM	Signal Phase And Timing Extended Message
SPU	Sensor Processing Unit
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TL	Traffic Light
TMC	Traffic Management Centre (PoDIUM platform side)
TMS	Traffic Management System (Operator/City side)
TPA	Trusted Platform Agent
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2P	Vehicle-to-Pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
VAM	VRU Awareness Messages
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network

Executive Summary

PoDIUM aims to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure to address the challenges in road automation and telecommunications, especially those linked with connectivity, cooperation, data management, interoperability and reliability, trust and data truthfulness, in order to foster the development of advanced Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions. This deliverable provides a detailed specification of the PoDIUM platform architecture that will enable these developments. It will guarantee, on a conceptual level, the interoperability between all Living Labs.

The document presents a detailed description of the developed architecture. The description is structured into five different views: the high-level view, the communication view, the functional view, the data flow and storage view, and the software security and data truthfulness view. Each view addresses different aspects of the PoDIUM architecture, allowing the experts of each field to focus on the view of interest.

This deliverable is intended for stakeholders and experts involved in the development of cooperative, connected, and automated mobility systems. It ensures that the system meets the identified stakeholders' needs and requirements. The demonstration of the use cases in the Living Labs will further validate the system's functionality and showcase its potential impact on improving CCAM.

1. Introduction

This section shortly introduces the PoDIUM project, outlines the purpose of this document, and identifies the intended audience.

1.1. Project Introduction

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UCs) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs (LLs) in Germany, Italy, and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for the availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) platform. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability, and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advanced data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards Digital Twins (DTs).
- New Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust, and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange, and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with the integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The aim of PoDIUM is to enhance CCAM services in Europe. To reach this goal, the project focuses on the development and integration of the PDI needed to ensure the vehicle's connectivity via certain network technologies. A total of five PoDIUM UCs will be tested and validated under real-life conditions in the three LLs, located in Germany, Spain, and Italy. These UCs require advancing several technologies and elements that will be integrated under the common PoDIUM architecture. In previous deliverables, a set of requirements have been specified.

The objective of Deliverable 3.1 is to present the common reference architecture of the PoDIUM platform. The aim of this architecture is to cover all UCs to ensure interoperability of the various heterogeneous networks and software components. This will guarantee, on a conceptual level, the interoperability between all LLs.

1.3. Intended audience

This deliverable is classified as “Public”, therefore, it will be uploaded on the PoDIUM website, where it will be available for all project partners and any interested readers, as stakeholders and experts involved in the development of CCAM systems. Nevertheless, the consortium members are the main intended audience of this document.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

Deliverable 3.1 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 describes the high-level architecture.
- Section 3 describes the communication view of the architecture.
- Section 4 describes the functional view of the architecture.
- Section 5 describes the data flow and storage view of the architecture.
- Section 6 describes the Information Technology (IT) environment view of the architecture.
- Section 7 describes the software integrity and data truthfulness view to the architecture.
- Section 8 serves as a conclusion, summarizing the key points of the deliverable.

The developed architecture implements the results of work package 2: “Requirements and Specifications”, where, among others, requirements for the platform and UCs have been formulated.

It will serve as a basis for the technical developments in the other tasks (3.2-3.5) of work package 3 and serve as a reference for the LLs integration in work package 4.

2. High-Level Architecture

This chapter describes the high-level PoDIUM reference architecture, with its main components, concepts and characteristics. Figure 1 shows the high-level architecture. The main components are the infrastructure sensors (together with a Sensor Processing Unit (SPU) or operating independently) as well as Road-Side Units (RSUs) offering communication and computation capabilities on the road level and the different platform services on the edge or cloud level that are needed to implement the different UCs.

Figure 1 High-level architecture

The basic communication technologies of PoDIUM are wired, cellular (5G-FR1 cm-wave, 5G-FR2 mm-wave) and ad-hoc (60 Ghz-WLAN, ITS-G5, SL-PC5) networks. The project classifies the communication as either direct, hybrid or with multi-connectivity. For further details on the communication aspects, refer to Section 3.

The road is equipped with: RSUs, connected sensors connected to the system through SPUs or directly, and connected Traffic Lights (TLs) (omitted from figure for simplicity, but similar to SPU).

The supported road users are: legacy (non-connected) vehicles and other non-connected road users; connected VRUs with a cellular User Equipment (UE); Connected conventional Vehicles (CV), connected Emergency Vehicles (EV) and Connected Automated Vehicles (CAV) with an On-Board Unit (OBU). For further details on the infrastructure and the road users, refer to Section 3.

The platform services are either hosted on a MEC server or on the central cloud. This is mainly determined by the latency requirements (as identified in the previous deliverables D2.1-D2.3 [1]-[3] from work package 2). For further details about the platform services and the IT environment, refer to Section 4 and Section 6, respectively.

To ensure the integrity of the software and exchanged CCAM data, a Trusted computing approach is developed on Trusted Platform Modules (TPMs). For further details on the software integrity aspects refer to Section 7. Many services depend on the DT, which fuses incoming information from different

sources (e.g. C-ITS messages and infrastructure sensor data) into an enhanced environmental model. Thus, the reliability of the DT data and, in consequence, of its sources is crucial. To reinforce this aspect, the PoDIUM architecture includes trust building and data truthfulness evaluation of data sources. For further details about the trust building and data truthfulness refer to Section 7.2.

This architecture is meant as a general blueprint of the concepts being developed in PoDIUM as part of several LLs and UCs. Thus, none of the UCs will provide all services and communication technologies, but each UC will implement a subset of them. This UC specific implementation will be specified in subsequent deliverables.

3. Communication View

This chapter describes the communication view of the PoDIUM reference architecture. Its goal is to specify a communication view covering the different communication technologies and solutions supported across the LLs and UCs.

3.1. Overview

The communication view describes the PoDIUM communicating entities, the communication technologies utilized among those entities as well as, from a communication engineering perspective, how multi-connectivity is implemented for enhanced reliability and reduced latency. The global high-level communication view specified for the PoDIUM platform is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: High-level communication view platform architecture.

This communication view serves as an abstract representation of the PoDIUM communication architecture covering the diverse requirements of various LLs and UCs. This standards-compliant overarching platform fosters efficient communication, data exchange, and collaboration between different entities within each UC.

3.2. Levels of Communication

The communication view in PoDIUM is divided into two layers, a Road level and the Cloud level:

- The **Road level** consists of mobile and stationary devices used by end-users on the road for communication and data processing:
 - o **User Equipment:** A UE is a term used in LTE/5G wireless communications to describe a mobile device, such as a smartphone, tablet, laptop, or other type of wireless device that is used to access the network. In PoDIUM, all UEs support cm-Wave communications.

- o **On-Board Units:** OBUs are wireless communication devices integrated into vehicles. In PoDIUM, all OBUs are equipped with cm-Wave communications. OBUs may additionally support 5G mm-Wave and/or ad-hoc wireless network communication (Sidelink (SL) and/or ITS-G5 and/or 60GHz WLAN). If an OBU supports ad-hoc communication, then the vehicle can exchange data directly with other road level devices in its vicinity.
- o **Road Side Unit:** RSUs are stationary wireless and/or wireline communication devices, which collect traffic data from a static sensing area along a road, and transmit data to traffic control devices at the Road level or to central traffic management centers at the Cloud Layer, or to nearby CVs equipped with OBUs [4].
- o **Sensor Processing Unit:** SPUs are stationary wireless and/or wireline communication devices, that are equipped with sensors such as cameras and lidar. They collect and process perception data from the sensors and transmit this information either directly to entities in the Cloud Layer for processing or to the RSU for relaying
- The **Cloud/Edge Layer** provides computer system resources, especially data storage and computing. Notice that the communication view does not draw a distinction between a regional or remote placement of the computing entities as long as they are centralized, i.e. the computing entities process centrally data from/for multiple geographically distributed road level system devices.
 - o **Multi-access Edge Computing:** MEC is a network architecture concept that enables cloud computing capabilities and an IT service environment at the edge of the cellular network. The basic idea behind MEC is that by running applications and performing related processing tasks closer to the cellular customer, network congestion is reduced and applications perform better, especially in terms of latency (quoted from [5]). A MEC Server can be directly accessed by Road Level System devices connected to the cellular networks. A MEC Server can also be accessed stationary Road Level System devices connected to wireline networks.
 - o **Cloud Computing:** A Cloud Server connected to the Internet is accessible by Road Level System devices connected via cellular networks and with stationary Road Level System devices connected via wireline networks.

3.3. Communication Technology

The major communication technologies deployed and used within the different PoDIUM UCs are:

- **Cellular network communication**, also called mobile network communication, uses a telecommunication network where the link to and from any end-user device is wireless. The network is distributed over land areas called cells, each served by at least one fixed-location base station, which links the device used by an end-user with a radio and core network connected to other wireless end users, Public Land Mobile Networks and the Internet. Examples include GSM (Global System for Mobile communication), LTE (Long Term Evolution), and 5G SA (5th Generation Stand Alone). The cellular network can provide a Point-to-Point (P2P) and/or Point-to-Multipoint (P2M) connections between end user devices served by it. It also can provide a P2P and/or P2M connection between end user devices served by it and

external data networks (e.g. the Internet, other cellular or wireline networks) (adapted from [6]).

- o **5G cm-Wave** identifies any wireless communication in Frequency Range 1 (FR1) in 5G mobile networks. FR1 was defined for frequency bands between 450 MHz and 6 GHz, which support a channel bandwidth between 5 MHz and 100 MHz. 5G cm-Wave typically provides wide area coverage and can offer low latency and high throughput rates.
- o **5G mm-Wave** identifies any wireless communication in Frequency Range 2 (FR2) in 5G mobile networks. FR2 was defined for frequency bands between 24.25 GHz and 52.60 GHz, which support a channel bandwidth between 50 MHz and 400 MHz. 5G mm-Wave provides restricted (local) coverage but can combine very high throughput rates with very low latency.
- **Ad-hoc wireless network communication** employs hardware and software protocols, such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth or Sidelink (SL) based on cellular radio technologies, and software protocols to create P2P and/or P2M networks, autonomously managed, enabling end-user devices to communicate without relying on cellular network infrastructure, wireless access points or any other traditional network infrastructure equipment.
 - o **60 GHz WLAN**, or IEEE 802.11ad is an amendment to the IEEE 802.11 Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) standard, developed to provide a Multiple Gigabit Wireless System (MGWS) standard at 60 GHz frequency (copied from [7]). 60 GHz WLAN provides restricted (local) coverage but can combine very high throughput rates with very low latency.
 - o **ITS-G5**, or IEEE 802.11p is another amendment to the IEEE 802.11 WLAN standard to add wireless access in vehicular environments, for a vehicular communication system. It defines enhancements to 802.11 required to support Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) applications [8]. ITS-G5 provides restricted (local) coverage with moderate to low throughput rates combined with very low latency.
 - o **SL (PC5)**: Sidelink refers to direct communication between UEs without the data going through the network. 3GPP release 14 defines the sidelink communication based on the so-called PC5 interface of the 4G LTE. We use the term SL (PC5) in the rest of the document. It is not until release 16, that 3GPP defined a new sidelink standard based on the New Radio (NR) 5G interface, SL (NR). A direct communications interface, as SL (PC5), enables Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communications, Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) communications, and Vehicle-to-Pedestrians (V2P) or other VRUs' communications, to provision low-latency and high-reliability vehicular services. The SL (PC5) interface does not necessarily require assistance from a mobile network and provides restricted (local) coverage with moderate to low throughput rates combined with very low latency.
- **Wired communication** relies on telecommunications networks where the link to and from any end-user device is wire-based. Examples include telephone networks, cable television or fixed-line internet access, and fibre-optic communication. The wired communication network can provide a P2P and/or P2M connections between end user devices served by it. It also can provide a P2P and/or P2M connection between end user devices served by it and external data networks (e.g. the Internet, other cellular or wireline networks) [9]. Wired connection has the

capability to provide very low latency with very high throughput rates, for instance when dark fibre is used.

3.4. Type of Communication

Normally, a single communication technology, as described in chapter 3.3, is used to transmit and receive data. In PoDIUM, new forms of connectivity are implemented that combine different communication technologies. Thus, the PoDIUM architecture supports and implements the following three forms of connectivity:

- **Single-Connectivity:** Only a single technology is used for the communication of two endpoints.
- **Multi-Connectivity:** Certain communication devices are endowed with multi-connectivity (Figure 2). By multi-connectivity we define the ability of communication devices to intelligently schedule messages and data packets over the different available communication technologies. This scheduling is equivalent to making decisions on the mapping of messages and packets to outgoing communication interfaces which allows a granular decision on the mapping of messages or message types to a number of available communication technologies. The multi-connectivity approach is followed to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the PDI system approach, and can also lead to improved latency.
- **Hybrid Communication:** In this approach, messages are simultaneously transmitted over all available communication technologies. Messages and data packets are always duplicated so that they can be transmitted on every available communication technology. High redundancy is realized with no regards to the criticality of individual messages and data packets.

3.5. Platform Communication Architecture View

The general communication view of Figure 2 is extended into a more granular view in Figure 3, in which all the communication devices of the PoDIUM UCs are included.

The **Cloud/Edge Layer** is divided into the **Edge Layer**, where MEC is applied, and the **Cloud Layer**, in which computing and storage resources are provided remotely and accessed via the Internet. Some arrows are drawn as a combination of wireless (dashed red) and wired (blue) indicating the use of both technologies end-to-end. For example, arrow between the EV and the cloud computing entity, indicates that the EV uses a cellular network (dashed red part of the arrow) to get connected to the Internet over a wired network (through the blue part of the arrow) for its communication connection to the cloud computing server. In this case two different communication technologies are used in sequence to connect the two entities.

Figure 3: Communication view platform architecture.

The OBU are deployed into the following communication entities:

- **Connected Vehicle:** A CV is a vehicle equipped with wireless communication technologies that enable data transfer with other vehicles, infrastructure or other networks [10].
- **Connected and Automated Vehicle:** A CAV is a vehicle equipped with the necessary hardware and software to wirelessly communicate with the world around it (other vehicles, traffic signals, the cloud, etc.) and perform part or all of the real-time operational and tactical functions required to operate in on-road traffic [11].
- **Emergency Vehicle:** An EV is a vehicle used by emergency services. An EV is a vehicle equipped with wireless communications.

The UE is implemented in the following communication devices:

- **Vulnerable Road User:** A VRU is defined in the ITS Directive as "non-motorised road users, such as pedestrians and cyclists as well as motor-cyclists and persons with disabilities or reduced mobility and orientation" [12].
- **Shuttle User:** Person using a UE to request pick-up from a transport system operating at short request on a short route between two places.

An additional stationary communication device is present:

- **Traffic Light:** A TL is a signalling device positioned at road intersections, pedestrian crossings, and other locations in order to control the flow of traffic [13].

4. Functional View

This chapter describes the functional view of the PoDIUM reference architecture. The functional view represents the interactions of the different PoDIUM functions and includes a description of each functionality.

4.1. Overview

Figure 4 describes, in high-level, the major blocks of the PoDIUM *Platform Services* and their main functional connections to the *Sensors and Actors*, and to the *Road Users* (including CVs, CAVs, EVs and VRUs). The interactions of the functions are depicted by arrows.

Figure 4: Overview of the functional view.

4.2. Platform Services Functions

PoDIUM Platform Services comprise the main functions necessary for the implementation of the PoDIUM UCs, namely *Traffic Management and/or Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning*, *Digital Twin*, *Risk Management*, *C-ITS Message and User Handling*, and *Software Integrity*. Depending on the implementation, these services can be hosted in the cloud, the edge, or locally.

4.2.1. Traffic Management and/or Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning

This function includes the traffic management subfunctions, which direct traffic on a strategic and macro level, and also incorporates the functionality on cooperative manoeuvre planning, which directs vehicles on a micro level (e.g., advising on cooperative lane changes). This function receives data from the *DT* and *Risk Management* functions and provides information to the other elements via the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* function.

4.2.2. Digital Twin

This function is responsible for creating the digital representation of the road. It collects the data from the different data sources (e.g. sensor or vehicle data) and fuses the data together to provide a complete state of all road users. It can contain functionalities related to data truthfulness/reliability (trust building) and the tracking of road users. It receives data from the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* function or also from 3rd parties, if needed, and provides information to the *Traffic Management and Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning* and the *Risk Management* functionalities.

4.2.3. Risk Management

This function estimates risks regarding a collision between different road users. It uses data from the *DT* and provides the data to the *Traffic Management and Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning*; it may also provide information to the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* to send out warnings.

4.2.4. C-ITS Message and User Handling

This function is the main function providing connectivity to the road users (like CAVs, VRUs, ...). It generates C-ITS messages from the data, chooses (in case of multi-connectivity) how the messages are transmitted (scheduling), transmits and receives messages, and also manages the connection information of the different users. It exchanges information with the *Traffic Management and Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning* and provides the received data to the *DT*.

4.2.5. Software Integrity

The *Software Integrity* function provides the attestation procedures of OBUs and RSUs in order to establish their integrity by means of periodic challenges to the OBUs and RSUs. It can report the deauthorization of a node in order to block its transmissions in the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* function.

4.3. Road User Functions

Figure 5 shows an overview on the *Road User* functions grouped into three high-level categories:

- **Connected Conventional and Emergency Vehicle Functions:** CVs and EVs are manually driven vehicles, which can communicate with the infrastructure via different communication technologies. These functions provide data to the infrastructure and inform the driver, via a Human-Machine Interface (HMI), about information received from the infrastructure.
- **Connected Automated Vehicle Functions:** CAVs use their sensors and information from the infrastructure for their automated driving function. These functions also provide information to the platform and follow platform instructions.
- **VRU Functions:** These functions contain all the subfunctions related to VRU devices.

In the following, the details of each function belonging to each category are provided as per Figure 5.

Figure 5: Overview of Road Users functions.

4.3.1. Common Road User Functions

The functions, which are used in each of the three road user function categories, are described in this subsection.

4.3.1.1. C-ITS Message Handling

This is the main function providing connectivity to the road users like CAVs, VRUs, etc. It generates C-ITS messages from the data, chooses how the messages are transmitted, transmits and receives messages and also manages the connection information between different users.

4.3.1.2. HMI Application for Cooperative Awareness in the Vehicle

This application runs in a vehicle and displays the results of the Cooperative Awareness service, which is a map with the current positions of the neighbouring vehicles.

4.3.1.3. Localization / Positioning

This function provides the raw data to localize the vehicle and position itself on the road. It also provides positioning data as input in messages for other functionalities, if needed.

4.3.1.4. Software Integrity

This function provides attestation procedures of OBUs and RSUs and may report the deauthorization of certain nodes in order to block their transmissions.

4.3.1.5. Local Dynamic Map

The Local Dynamic Map (LDM) is the function that accesses the database where all the information about the road elements and users is stored. It is populated with received information from C-ITS messages and road sensors, and provides information to applications and services requiring it.

4.3.2. Additional Functions for Connected Automated Vehicles

In addition to the common road user functions, the following functions are required for the category *connected automated vehicle functions*.

4.3.2.1. Automated Driving Function: Perception

Perception is the collection and processing of sensor data needed for automated driving functions within a vehicle. Data from several sources are combined to provide a better basis for analysis in further steps. This includes the tracking of other road users.

4.3.2.2. Automated Driving Function: Planning

This function utilizes perception data with other information, such as high-definition maps, to generate routes and trajectories to fulfil automated driving tasks.

4.3.2.3. Automated Driving Function: Motion Control

This function contains the capability of the vehicle to execute planned actions, from the planning function, by controlling vehicle parameters such as steering, acceleration and deceleration.

4.3.3. Additional Functions for Vulnerable Road Users

In addition to the common road user functions, the following functions are required for the category *VRU functions*.

4.3.3.1. HMI Application for VRUs

The HMI function runs on VRU's end user devices and displays information for VRUs.

4.3.3.2. Navigation

This block refers to a turn-by-turn navigation application that guides users through a chosen route from a source to a destination. The application will share the current physical location and the predicted future path of the VRU (or at least a part of it) with PoDIUM platform functions. This information will be used to increase the safety level by predicting potential hazardous situations that may involve the user and other vehicles.

4.4. Sensors and Actors Functions

An overview on Sensor and Actors Functions is depicted in Figure 6. Descriptions of these functions are provided in the following subsections.

Figure 6: Overview Sensors and Actor Functions

4.4.1. Infrastructure-based Road User Detection

This function detects road users. It analyses the infrastructure-collected sensor data, to provide advanced detection and perception capabilities to the platform.

4.4.1.1. Sensor Data Collection

This function collects data from the different sensors for further analysis.

4.4.1.2. Road User Detector

This function uses the raw sensor (e.g. camera, radar, lidar) data to detect road users. A detection contains, e.g., the position, the pose, and the class of an object. The detector is usually based on machine learning techniques.

4.4.2. Traffic Lights

This function provides typical functionalities at TL-controlled intersections. It detects vehicles and provides information to the platform, but also performs actions to support traffic management decisions within the platform.

5. Data Flow and Storage View

This chapter describes the data flow and storage view of the PoDIUM reference architecture.

5.1. Overview

The data flow view provides a global picture (see Figure 7) of the management of information within the PoDIUM architecture, showing the types of information exchanged by the different functional blocks, in compliance with the classification of chapter 4.

The view clearly illustrates the standards-oriented approach used by the project, as many data types (those for which standardized messages exist) have been already identified and specified as messages by European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). In some cases, the need of extending the message is identified, in order to support some innovative functionality not covered by the standard, as explained in more detail in the following sections.

The data management architecture described in this chapter will be instantiated, with suitable customisation, by each of the PoDIUM UC, as part of next WP3 activities. Among them, task T3.4 is devoted to the semantic interoperability, and will take this data flow view as a starting point for a deeper analysis of each of the data exchanges, in the context of each interaction between elements of the architecture in each use case. The results will be described in the future project deliverables D3.2 and D3.3

5.2. Data Flow and Storage components description

As mentioned above, the building blocks of the data view are inspired by the functional view of chapter 4, and the present section briefly describes the kind of data exchanged by each block with other blocks of the architecture.

The order for describing functional blocks in the present section is different of the order used in chapter 4 because, in most cases, the kind of information managed by the services is easier to understand if introduced and explained in contexts closer to the road users and infrastructure than if explained in the more abstract context of the platform services. For this reason, the structure of this section mentions road users and sensors first and platform services afterwards.

5.2.1. Road Users

This section contains information about the type of data exchanged by the elements of the *Road Users* block of the architecture (Figure 7), i.e., the *Connected Conventional & Emergency Vehicle*, the *Connected Automated Vehicle*, the *VRU Device & App* and the *Shuttle User App*.

5.2.1.1. Connected Conventional & Emergency Vehicle

This block covers the functionality of CVs and EVs that are connected and interact with PoDIUM services, but have no automated driving capabilities.

Figure 7: Overview of the data flow view.

These vehicles exchange the following types of information with the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* services:

- Share their position and speed, as well as other specific information of the Awareness Service, by means of ETSI Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAM) [14] with the necessary extensions to support the PoDIUM innovative functionalities.
- Share the origin and destination of their current trip with PoDIUM services, for specific functionalities related with traffic optimization in general and for EV. This information may need definition of new messages not covered by ETSI standards.
- Receive ETSI Cooperative Perception Messages (CPM) [15] from PoDIUM services.
- Receive cooperative manoeuvres recommendations, as well as optimal route recommendations in the format of ETSI Manoeuvre Coordination Message (MCM) [16] with suitable extensions.
- Receive collision risk alerts in the form of ETSI Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM) [17].
- Receive ETSI In-Vehicle Information Messages (IVIM) [18].

In addition, the vehicles:

- exchange bilaterally CAM messages [14], as well as CPM messages [15] with other CVs, EVs and CAVs.

5.2.1.2. Connected Automated Vehicle

The CAV block covers all the functionality considered for the CV plus the capability for automated driving. This implies some additional data exchanges with PoDIUM *ITS Message and User Handling* services, namely:

- Exchange bilaterally ETSI CPM [15] messages with PoDIUM services that, for some innovative functionalities, shall require extensions to include information about:
 - o Uncertainties about the road users' states.
 - o Prediction of future trajectories of road users.
 - o Sensor data.

In addition, CAVs:

- receive attestation messages from *Software Integrity* service to check the integrity of the software in the vehicle.

Finally, some CAVs, those that provide shuttle transport services, exchange bilaterally information with the *Shuttle Management Services* of the PoDIUM platform:

- CAV location/status (the use of a suitable ETSI message or an extension will be decided in a future stage of the project).
- Specific tele-supervision commands.
- Real Time Kinematic (RTK) connections.

5.2.1.3. VRU Device & App

VRUs in some PoDIUM UCs shall be equipped with a mobile device and app providing the HMI and other functionalities (localisation, etc.) related to the PoDIUM services.

The device and app exchange information with PoDIUM *C-ITS Message and User Handling* services, namely:

- Sending ETSI VRU Awareness Messages (VAM) [19]
 - Including the position and speed of VRUs.
 - Optionally with some extensions or modifications, to support the PoDIUM innovative functionality of uncertainties management.
- Sending user registration requests to VRU management services, in order to provide and authorize the use of the personal information within the service.
- Exchange bilaterally and receiving from the infrastructure ETSI MCM Messages [16].
- Receive collision risk alerts in the form of ETSI DENM messages [17].
- Receive other risk alerts for specific functionalities whose content and availability of standard ETSI message will be evaluated in a future stage of the development.

5.2.1.4. Shuttle User App

Some PoDIUM services support specific functionality for the passengers of a connected shuttle vehicle. These passengers shall make use of their smartphones and the PoDIUM *Shuttle User App* which, in turn, shall send some information to the PoDIUM Shuttle Management services, namely:

- Service requests.
- User state.

5.2.2. Sensors & Actors

This section contains information about the type of data exchanged by the elements of the "Sensors & Actors" block of the architecture (Figure 7), i.e., the *Infrastructure-based Road User Detection*, the *Traffic Controllers* and the *Traffic Management System (TMS)*.

5.2.2.1. Infrastructure-based Road User Detection

Different kinds of sensors that support road user detection functionalities are integrated in PoDIUM UCs. The corresponding results are sent to the PoDIUM DT services via:

- ETSI CAM (Cooperative Awareness Messages) [14].
- ETSI CPM (Cooperative Perception Message) [15].
- For the detections of VRU by means of Artificial Intelligence Cameras (indicating location, position, type of user and predicted trajectory), a suitable format will be selected or designed in a future stage of the project, being ETSI VAM (VRU Awareness Messages) [25] one of the alternatives considered.

5.2.2.2. Traffic Controllers

Traffic controllers are highly specialised infrastructure devices that control the TL of one (or several) intersection(s), and integrate the information from infrastructure sensors (like magnetic loops). They may have connection with the central traffic management system of their city or area, and are capable of executing traffic strategies in an autonomous (intersections keep their safety even if the traffic controllers lose connection with the central management system), semi-autonomous or centralised way.

In the context of PoDIUM, the traffic controllers exchange data with the TMS of the urban area, which acts as an intermediary with PoDIUM services. They perform the following actions:

- Forward data collected from the traffic sensors.
- Receive traffic plans (signal times).

- Manage priority requests for EV (get green light for a particular TL as soon as possible but respecting security restrictions).

5.2.2.3. Traffic Management Systems

This category includes urban traffic management systems (that have traffic controllers connected to them), road and tunnel control systems and pre-existing systems that shall be integrated with the PoDIUM UCs but are not PoDIUM platform services themselves. These systems are not to be confused with the group of PoDIUM services with similar name described in sections 4.2.1 and 5.2.3.2.

These systems shall be integrated in PoDIUM architecture in such way that they:

- Share the map information about the road infrastructure that they control, in ETSI MAP Extended Message (MAPEM) [18] format, with PoDIUM *Traffic Management & Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning* services.
- Send to PoDIUM *Traffic Management & Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning* services:
 - ETSI Signal Phase And Timing Extended Messages (SPATEM) [18] containing the status and timing of the TLs.
 - ETSI DENM messages [17].
 - ETSI IVIM messages [18].
- Send a variety of traffic data concepts to both the PoDIUM *Traffic management & cooperative manoeuvre* services and to the PoDIUM *DT*, with contents beyond the scope of ETSI messages; so, specific messages shall probably be designed in a future stage of the project.
- Receive from PoDIUM *Traffic management & cooperative manoeuvre* services, i.e.,:
 - Priority requests for EV that shall in turn be sent to the Traffic Controllers.
 - Strategic selection of an optimal traffic plan, produced by a specific service dedicated to processing data from connected vehicles, and that, in turn, shall be translated into a suitable traffic plan for each Traffic Controller.

5.2.3. Platform Services

This section contains information about the type of data exchanged by the elements of the *Platform services* block of the architecture (Figure 7), i.e., the *C-ITS Message and User Handling*, the *Traffic Management & Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning*, the *Digital Twin*, the *Risk Management*, the *Software Integrity* and the *Shuttle Management* services.

5.2.3.1. C-ITS Message and User Handling

These services have a crucial role implementing the communication mechanisms with the road users, making use of the suitable protocols and channels. They mainly act between road users and other PoDIUM services. The information they exchange with road users has been already described in section 5.2.1. The information they exchange with other PoDIUM services is of the following form:

- Send to the *DT*:
 - ETSI VAM messages [19] received from VRUs.
 - ETSI CAM messages [14] received from vehicles.
 - Origin and destination of trips received from vehicles.
- Send to and receive from *DT*:
 - ETSI CPM messages [15], optionally with extensions, containing:
 - Uncertainties about the road users' states.

- Prediction of future trajectories of road users.
 - Sensor data.
 - ETSI MCM messages [16].
 - Sensor data.
- Receive from the *DT*:
 - Awareness info.
 - Traffic status information.
 - A specific service shall be in charge of combining this information with the trip origin and destination sent by each vehicle and elaborate, a particular route recommendation to be sent to each one.
- Receive from *Traffic Management & Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning* services:
 - (Cooperative) manoeuvre recommendations (in the format of ETSI MCM messages [16] or other PODIUM-specific formats).
 - Road hazards and traffic incidents in the format of DENM messages [18] (or another PoDIUM-specific format)
 - ETSI IVIM messages [18].
- Receive from *Risk Management* services:
 - ETSI DENM messages [17].
- Receive from *Software Integrity* services authorization and deauthorization requests.

5.2.3.2. Traffic Management & Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning

This category includes a set of PoDIUM platform services implementing functionalities related to traffic management, either regarding strategies at a macroscopic level or by means of cooperative manoeuvres at a microscopic level. They should not to be confused with the TMS themselves, mentioned in section 5.2.2.3, integrated in the UCs, but not actual PoDIUM services

These services exchange the following kinds of information:

- Receive from *TMS* (see section 5.2.2.3, for more details):
 - ETSI MAPEM messages [18].
 - ETSI SPATEM messages [18].
 - ETSI DENM messages [17].
 - ETSI IVIM messages [18].
- Send to *TMS*:
 - Priority requests for EVs that are in turn sent to the Traffic Controllers.
 - Strategic selection of an optimal traffic plan.
- Send to road users, via the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* service:
 - (Cooperative) manoeuvre recommendations in the format of ETSI MCM messages [16] or another PoDIUM-specific format.
 - Road hazards and traffic incidents in the format of DENM messages [18] (or another PoDIUM-specific format).
 - ETSI IVIM messages [18].
- Receive from the *DT*:

- o The position and speed of EVs (in ETSI CPM format [15]).
- o The position and speed of CVs (in ETSI CPM format [15]).
- o Uncertainties about the road users' states (using an extension of ETSI CPM messages [15]).
- o Prediction of future trajectories of road users (using an extension of ETSI CPM messages [15]).
- o Road hazards and traffic incidents.
- Exchange bilaterally with the *DT*:
 - o Traffic data that covers multiple aspects, including traffic sensors and metrics, or traffic plans and strategies.
- Send to *Shuttle Management* services:
 - o Traffic status (per road segment)

5.2.3.3. Digital Twin

The DT:

- Exchanges with *C-ITS Message and User Handling* multiple kinds of information that were already described in section 5.2.3.1.
- Receives from the *Infrastructure-based Road User Detection* elements:
 - o ETSI CAM messages [14].
 - o ETSI CPM messages [15].
 - o Detections of road users (location, position, destination), in a format that shall be designed in a future stage of the project.
- Receives from *TMS*:
 - o Traffic data with contents beyond the scope of ETSI messages; so, specific messages shall probably be designed in a future stage of the project.
- Exchanges bilaterally with the PoDIUM *Traffic Management & Cooperative Manoeuvre* services
 - o Traffic data that covers multiple aspects, including traffic sensors and metrics, or traffic plans and strategies.
- Sends to *Risk Management* services:
 - o ETSI CPM messages [15], including:
 - CV's position, speed and classification.
 - VRU's positions and speed.
- Exchanges with *Software Integrity* services:
 - o Read/tag messages.

5.2.3.4. Risk Management

The *Risk Management* services:

- Receive from *DT* and take as input:
 - o ETSI CPM messages [15], including:
 - CV's position, speed and classification.
 - VRU's position and speed.

- Produce as output and send to road users via the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* services:
 - ETSI DENM messages [17] with:
 - Collision risk warnings and parameters.

5.2.3.5. Software Integrity

The *Software Integrity* services interact with other services and elements for checking their integrity. They:

- Exchange Read/tag messages with the *DT*.
- Send authorisation/deauthorisation messages to the *C-ITS Message and User Handling* services.
- Send attestation messages to *CAVs* and *RSUs*

5.2.3.6. Shuttle Management Services

These are PoDIUM services that support specific functionality for the passengers of a connected shuttle vehicle. They exchange information with the:

- *Shuttle User App*:
 - Service requests.
 - User state.
- *CAVs* (those that provide shuttle transport services):
 - CAV's location/status (the use of a suitable ETSI message or an extension shall be decided in a future stage of the project).
 - Specific tele-supervision commands.
 - RTK connections.

6. IT Environment View

This chapter describes the Information Technology (IT) environment view of the PoDIUM reference architecture. The target is to describe where the applications are running and how they are deployed across all UCs.

Two areas have been foreseen as target environments at different levels of the PoDIUM platform: road, and edge/cloud. The components span these levels and host the different running software services. Software services are omitted for simplicity.

6.1. Overview

The IT environment view describes the deployment environment of services and the foreseen storage Databases (DB) instances. It lists the hardware elements and the deployment management framework used for services and applications, i.e., hardware virtualization and containerization of software components respectively.

Figure 8: IT environment view of platform architecture

Although PoDIUM UCs differ significantly, their constituting services are deployed in similar hardware component patterns. The identified elements of the PoDIUM IT environment view are depicted in Figure 8; and a description of each follows in the rest of this section.

6.2. IT components description

Regarding the hardware used, the possible types are bare metal and virtualization; in the first case the dedicated servers with independent and exclusive resources are employed, with dedicated memory, disk and Central Processing Units (CPUs) and, in some of the cases, with Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), while also dedicated maintenance and server management are required. In the second case, the hardware is virtualized, meaning that the whole server, together with memory and storage, are instantiated from a set of resources, and are shared with other services. This is the approach usually

adopted by cloud services, which are not highly loaded and which do not involve any specialized or high duty operations.

Regarding the software deployment, the options are to run natively or in a containerized manner. In the first choice, PoDIUM will deploy native software when applications are proprietary solutions, such as automated driving controllers in CAVs or in attestation services, where the software must be securely anchored to the running hardware and containerization breaks this link.

With respect to containerized software services, we consider two options, the first one is to run static containers, and the second to manage clustered containers. The latter is the case of Kubernetes implementations where a set of services are customized for load balancing or scalability. Some cloud and edge services in UC2 are using this scheme.

6.2.1. Road Level

At the road level, the main hardware components identified are CAV/CV, RSU, SPU, Camera Sensor and VRU. All of them run specialized hardware which is described below. Some software is containerized and no hardware virtualization is required.

6.2.1.1. Connected and Automated Vehicles

CAVs are characterized by an On-Board Personal Computer (OB-PC) hosting automated driving functions and perception. In UC4 and UC5 automated driving services are native and proprietary on this OB-PC but, for other UCs these functions are containerized.

OB-PC is connected directly or via another communication hardware (HW) with Network Interface Cards (NICs), allowing either multi-connectivity and hybrid communications. OB-PCs interact with communications hardware, vehicle sensors and a user interface, running on dedicated hardware (usually a tablet) depending on the implementation present on-board. OB-PC communicates locally via a Controller Area Network (CAN) bus or in-vehicle ethernet Local Area Network (LAN).

The CAV/CV hardware also hosts a LDM, which can be seen as a DB supporting automated driving functionalities. Depending on the use case considered, the LDM is present on the OB-PC or in a dedicated OBU used for CCAM communication with short-range radio interfaces. The OBU has also containerized services for CCAM generation and runs also the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) and the attestation software which are natively linked to the hosting hardware. The placement of the 5G modem (or any other communication interface) depends on the use case, since it is directly connected to OBUs in some cases, or to internal generic communication hardware.

6.2.1.2. Sensor Processing Units

SPUs share with RSUs their location and most of their connectivity capabilities. RSUs, in fact, interact with road users via short range communications and usually do not require significant computing resources. SPUs are equipped with a main processor hardware, providing a GPU. SPU functionality runs in containerized services and without clustering deployment. Independent communication board/router with attached NICs separate connectivity from sensor functionality and handle redundancy in cases, such as multi-connectivity. Sensors are attached to the main hardware for processing within a local network.

6.2.1.3. Road Side Units

RSUs (without sensors) contain short range communications hardware plus the software to implement the ETSI ITS-G5 communication protocol stack. This software can natively run in the RSU's CPU, or can be virtualized in another device. For instance, in UC2 and UC3, the ITS-G5 communication protocol stack runs virtualized in the hardware of the edge.

In PoDIUM, other RSUs are also used, which are experimental RSUs with integrated pieces of hardware together with specialized processing capabilities to support either SPU or RSU functionalities. The use of network communication interfaces happens via communication hardware (router or intelligent switch) which concentrates NICs. Short range NICs are connected via an on-board hardware unit into the RSU.

6.2.1.4. Camera Sensor

Camera sensors are different from SPUs in the sense that are specific to UC2 and UC3 and do not process or just pre-process video in-place using their proprietary software.

6.2.1.5. Vulnerable Road Users

VRUs in PoDIUM contribute directly to the platform data as long as they use an application to interact with the system. These applications are strongly linked to the particular implementation. The running hardware are smartphones or tablets with 5G interface and, at this current state of the project, no containerization is considered in the implementation.

6.2.2. Cloud/Edge

Applications hosted at edge and cloud levels collect data from the field, elaborate it and interact with road side level. These platforms provide management, scalability, and connectivity modules to interact with all other actors involved. Edge and cloud levels have some differences that described below.

6.2.2.1. Cloud

Cloud services are run mostly on virtualized machines in public cloud infrastructure, with no or limited need of management by the users. Moreover, cloud services detach the software from being hardware dependent; consequently, hosted services may run anywhere and possibly migrate thanks to the virtualization/containerization and their deployment management.

6.2.2.2. Edge

Edge nodes are essentially dedicated servers. Edge nodes are placed in infrastructure data centres in the edge of the mobile network, closer to the user. Servers on the edge may require and host specialized resources, since in some of the cases specific models of GPUs are required.

In the edge, services are mostly deployed as containers, but at the moment, no scaling or clustering is considered, even if it can be easily added using common edge/cloud management software.

7. Software Integrity and Data Truthfulness

This section describes the software integrity verification approach in the PoDIUM platform as well as the approaches for data truthfulness.

7.1. Software Integrity

The remote attestation architecture establishes a framework for verifying the integrity of the software running on a device and to trigger proper countermeasures in case the software has been tampered with. The framework involves two roles, (1) the Remote Attestor, the entity responsible for challenging and verifying the trustworthiness of a remote device referred to be (2) a Trusted Computing Base (TCB). The TCB implements all technical capabilities to measure integrity and to generate integrity proofs in accordance with the Trusted Computing approach (e.g. a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) with proper Trusted Software Stack), as depicted in Figure 9. The TCB runs a Trusted Platform Agent (TPA), a secure software logic capable of interacting with the TPM and sending an integrity proof upon request by a Remote Attestor, in a process called Remote Attestation.

Figure 9 depicts the remote attestation architecture. The remote attestation is triggered by two different devices of the system at the edge and road levels. At road level, there are moving (autonomous) CVs equipped with a proper OBU which software integrity is challenged and then verified by the Remote Attestor into both RSUs and MEC Server. The MEC Server is also responsible for challenging and verifying software integrity of RSUs. In this view, both the OBU and RSU are TCBs.

Figure 9: High-level remote attestation architecture for verification of software integrity.

Figure 10 shows the internal software integrity architecture of a TCB (e.g. OBU or RSU) and of a Remote Attestor. The software integrity architecture depicted is described in D2.2 [2]. The main message useful to be recalled in this document, is that, such an architecture is responsible for implementing the Secure Boot(strap) and, (i) to measure the software components running at kernel and user space of the TCB, and (ii) to accumulate such measures into the Root of Trust for Storage (i.e. the TPM that provides a set of Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs) to securely accumulate the integrity measurements in the form of hashes. In detail, after loading the Linux Kernel, the Integrity Measurement Architecture

(IMA) [20][21], a security subsystem of the Linux kernel, becomes available and measures all files that match a given policy that are loaded and possibly executed. All measurement records are kept in memory in the so-called IMA log and an overall integrity checksum is retained using the PCR10 of the TPM.

Figure 10: Software Integrity Architecture within the TCB and Remote Attestor Architecture.

The IMA log and the value of PCRs accumulated into the TPM represents the key information for the Remote Attestor to verify, at run-time, the integrity of the software running into the TCB. In detail, remote attestation takes place according to the following sequence of actions:

1. Remote Attestor opens a communication channel with the target TCB and sends a *nonce* to the TCB.
2. TCB executes the TPM2_Quote [22], *i.e.* it signs the PCRs from 0 to 10 and the *nonce* using the private part of Attestation Key (AK).
3. TCB sends back to the Remote Attestor the Quote (*i.e.* the signature over the digest value of the PCR from 0 to 10 and the *nonce*), the PCR values, and the IMA log. Then:
4. Remote Attestor performs all checks to verify the TCB integrity:
 - a. It verifies the validity of the Quote using the public key embedded in the AK certificate (previously set as trusted), also including the *nonce*.
 - b. It verifies the integrity of the IMA log by recalculating the value of a “soft PCR” from the IMA log itself and comparing it with the value of PCR10.
 - c. It verifies the files included in the IMA log except for the files to be excluded against whitelists/blacklists of digests previously built and considered trusted by design.
 - d. The result of the integrity status can be: TRUSTED if all files in the IMA log are found in whitelists (also called golden values); UNKNOWN if at least one file in the IMA log is not found in whitelists, but no file is found in blacklists; and UNTRUSTED if at least one file in the IMA log is found in blacklists or if any of the previous checks fails.

- Finally, the Attestor closes the communication channel and takes the appropriate action(s)/countermeasure(s).

7.2. Data Truthfulness

As already described in Section 2, especially for the DT services, the reliability of its output and, in a direct consequence, the reliability of the information received to be fused into the DT is crucial. Thus, two approaches on different aspects of data truthfulness are integrated into the PoDIUM systems exemplarily. Figure 11 shows the general approach to check the data truthfulness. Before data from the different sources, e.g. infrastructure sensor data or CCAM data, are forwarded to the platform services, a reliability check is performed. The approaches for performing this check are detailed next.

Figure 11: General data truthfulness approach.

7.2.1. First Approach: Self-assessment of the Digital Twin Fusion Module

Figure 12 shows the first approach to ensure data truthfulness. It assesses the statistical assumptions in the data fusion step in the DT of the MEC.

Figure 12: Self-assessment for the Digital Twin.

The statistical assumptions are compared against the data coming from the different sources and checks whether the distribution of the data fits the assumptions [23]. For this, subjective logic is used [24]. This allows online assessment of each individual data source and also the assessment of each entity which is estimated based on this data.

For each assessed entity, a quality score in the range from zero to one is generated. The assessed entities can be, for example, the tracks of the objects of the DT or the different data sources.

7.2.2. Second Approach: Redundancy-based Sensor Data Fusion

The second approach is based on the fusion of data coming from different types of sensors that are sensing the same object as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Sensors' fusion and enhancement

This approach will reduce the occurrence of both false positives and false negatives. Moreover, different information can be fused, exploiting the strength of each sensor and/or combining data to enhance precision.

for each sensed object, an entry on the DT is generated, containing all the information coming from the different sensors fused in a proper way. Additionally, a data quality score is given to each object based on multiple factors including the number of sensors used.

8. Conclusions

In this document, we have described the architecture design developed within the PoDIUM project based on the requirements derived in previous deliverables. It builds upon existing standards and approaches from previous projects, extending them, if necessary, to include the contributions of PoDIUM in the field of CCAM, especially:

- the multi-connectivity approach,
- the realization of DTs based on advanced data fusion and integrated on MECs including hybrid data management,
- the respective C-ITS messages for connecting the road users themselves and with the infrastructure, and
- trust, i.e., the concept for ensuring software integrity as well as data truthfulness within the overall system.

The main PoDIUM components have been summarized in a high-level overview of the architecture.

Additionally, we provided several different detailed views, concentrating on communication, functions, data flow and storage, IT environment as well as software integrity and data truthfulness. Each view was given as a figure, accompanied by descriptions of the most relevant elements. Together, they form the overall architecture of the PoDIUM platform.

In the next step, based on this deliverable, the different UCs will derive their implementations of the platform to be realized in the three LLs in Germany, Italy, and Spain. These UC-specific implementations will be described first in D3.2, and their final status will be covered by D3.3.

References

- [1] Project PoDIUM. Deliverable D2.1, PoDIUM Use-cases Description and Specification. Online available soon: <https://podium-project.eu/library/#deliverables>
- [2] Project PoDIUM. Deliverable D2.2, PoDIUM Platform Requirements and Specification. Online available soon: <https://podium-project.eu/library/#deliverables>
- [3] Project PoDIUM. Deliverable D2.3, PoDIUM Availability and Cooperation Enablers Definition and Evaluation Data Specifications. Online available soon: <https://podium-project.eu/library/#deliverables>
- [4] [https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/roadsides#:~:text=A%20roadside%20unit%20\(RSU\)%20collects,a%20central%20traffic%20management%20center](https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/roadsides#:~:text=A%20roadside%20unit%20(RSU)%20collects,a%20central%20traffic%20management%20center), as of 03.08.2023.
- [5] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multi-access_edge_computing, as of 03.08.2023.
- [6] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cellular_network, as of 03.08.2023.
- [7] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IEEE_802.11ad, as of 03.08.2023.
- [8] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IEEE_802.11p, as of 03.08.2023.
- [9] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wired_communication, as of 03.08.2023.
- [10] <https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/CAV/cam-vocabulary/connected-vehicle/>, as of 03.08.2023
- [11] Key Terms for Connected & Automated Vehicles (CAV). Online. <https://portal.ct.gov/-/media/DOT/documents/dpolicy/CAV/Key-CAV-Terms-Updated-03-01-2021.pdf>, as of 03.08.2023.
- [12] [https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/intelligent-transport-systems/road/action-plan-and-directive/its-vulnerable-road-users_en#:~:text=Vulnerable%20Road%20Users%20\(VRU\)%20are,or%20reduced%20mobility%20and%20orientation%22](https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/intelligent-transport-systems/road/action-plan-and-directive/its-vulnerable-road-users_en#:~:text=Vulnerable%20Road%20Users%20(VRU)%20are,or%20reduced%20mobility%20and%20orientation%22), as of 03.08.2023.
- [13] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Traffic_light, as of 03.08.2023.
- [14] ETSI EN 302 637-2 Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Part 2: Specification of Cooperative Awareness Basic Service, 2019.
- [15] ETSI TR 103 562 Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Analysis of the Collective Perception Service (CPS); Release 2, 2019.
- [16] ETSI TS 103 561 Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communication; Basic Set of Application; Maneuver Coordination Service.
- [17] ETSI EN 302 637-3 Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Part 3: Specifications of Decentralized Environmental Notification Basic Service, 2019.
- [18] ETSI TS 103 301 Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Facilities layer protocols and communication requirements for infrastructure services; Release 2, 2021.
- [19] ETSI TS 103 300-3 Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) awareness; Part 3: Specification of VRU awareness basic service; Release 2, 2023.
- [20] Kasatkin, D.; Zohar, M. Integrity Measurement Architecture. Online. 2017. <https://sourceforge.net/p/linux-ima/wiki/Home>, as of 02.08.2023.
- [21] Sailer, R.; Zhang, X.; Jaeger, T.; van Doorn, L. Design and Implementation of a TCG-based Integrity Measurement Architecture. In Proceedings of the 13th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 04), San Diego, USA, 9–13 August 2004.
- [22] The Trusted Platform Module (TPM2.0) tools. Online. <https://tpm2-tools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>, as of 03.08.2023.

- [23] Griebel, T.; Müller, J.; Buchholz, M.; Dietmayer, K. Kalman Filter Meets Subjective Logic: A Self-Assessing Kalman Filter Using Subjective Logic. 2020 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION), Rustenburg, South Africa, 2020, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.23919/FUSION45008.2020.9190520.
- [24] Jøsang, A. Subjective logic. Springer, 2016.